

Cox Regression Analysis on Coronavirus Pandemic in Nigeria Using Rivers State as a Case Study

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 05 Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Cox regression Hazard Model Survival analysis Patient Pandemics Corona virus</p>	<p>The research is on the application of Cox proportional hazard model with a view to identify the factors that affect the survival and influence the death status of covid 19 patients. A secondary data from national centre for diseases control (NCDC) website on infected covid 19 patients was collected and used. The first case in Nigerian was recorded on 27th of February 2020 and likewise the first case was recorded in Rivers State on 21st of march 2020 which the dissertation covers from the first date of the recorded case to July 2020 based on daily recorded cases. The total number of recorded patients between the period was 23684. Regression was carry out using confirmed death on confirmed cases, confirmed death on discharge cases and confirmed death on total active. The result shows 98% (23227) were censored for confirmed death on confirmed cases, 89% (21183) were censored for confirmed death on discharge cases and 93% (22045) were confirmed death on discharge cases and COS regression shows that all have the same number of missing value of 13% of 14 and the same standard error for skeswnness and kurtosis which is .016 and .032 respectively. Since the COVID-19 pandemic is still ongoing, these findings need to be confirmed and investigated in future larger population studies.</p>

1. Introduction

Hazard models are category of survival models in statistics. Survival models narrate the time that passes before an event occurs to one or more covariates that may be connected with that quantity of time. It is defined as the probability that an individual who is exposed to the risk that an event might occur will experience that event within a particular period of time, given that the individual was exposed to the risk that the event might occur ([encyclopedia.com](https://www.encyclopedia.com)).

Survival analysis (also called failure time analysis) is a unique field of statistics that analyzes failure time and its probability on a group or groups of assets/individuals. Failure time is a described point event, often called failures, resulting after a period of time. Some examples of failure times include; the lifetimes of machine components in reliability field, the survival times of subjects in a clinical trial, and period of economic recessions in economics. Kleinbaum (1996) defined survival analysis as a statistical method for data analysis where the aftermath variable of interest is the time to the occurrence of an event. Therefore survival analysis is also called "time to event analysis". The time to the event of interest is termed either survival time or failure time. Survival analysis are widely used in medicine (known as hazard or survival models), economics (known as duration models), engineering (known as reliability models) and related fields, where they are used to analyze factors associated with the occurrence and timing of events such as time until recurrence of a disease, time to death, finding a job, marriage, divorce, birth of children, time to parole, lifetime of machines, etc. Survival analysis is a deep rooted area in statistical theory as well as in biostatistics. There are several books that covered survival analysis. Examples include; Lawless (2002) covering the parametric methods, Cox and Oakes (1984) which contributes to the recent theory used in survival analysis, Andersen and Gill (1982), where the Cox model was extended to general counting processes and also established the asymptotic properties of the associated Breslow,(1992), estimator of the cumulative baseline hazard function through an elegant counting process called Martingale theory (Fleming and Harrington, 1991).

According to Harrell, (2001) Cox proportion hazards is define as the trending model for the analysis of survival data. It is a semi-parametric model. it makes a parametric assumption concerning the effect of the predictors on the hazard function, but makes no assumption regarding the

nature of the hazard function $\lambda(t)$ itself. The Cox PH model assumes that predictors act multiplicatively on the hazard function but does not assume that the hazard function is constant (i.e., exponential model), Weibull, or any other particular form. The regression portion of the model is fully parametric; that is, the regressors are linearly related to log hazard or log cumulative hazard. In many situations, either the form of the true hazard function is unknown or it is complex, so the Cox model has definite advantages. Also, one is usually more interested in the effects of the predictors than in the shape of $\lambda(t)$, and the Cox approach allows the analyst to essentially ignore $\lambda(t)$, which is often not of primary interest.

According to Bewick et al, (2004), Cox proportional hazard is a branch of statistics that focus majorly with the death of biological organisms and the failure of mechanical systems. It is also sometimes referred to as a statistical method for analyzing survival data. Cox event history is also known as various other names, such as survival analysis, duration analysis, or transition analysis. Generally speaking, this technique involves the modeling of data structured in a time-to-event format. The goal of this analysis is to understand the probability of the occurrence of an event. Cox event history was primarily developed for use in medical and biological sciences. However, this technique is now frequently used in engineering as well as in statistical and data analysis.

One of the major aims of the cox proportional hazard technique is to explain the causes behind the differences or similarities between the events encountered by subjects. For instance, Cox regression may be used to evaluate why certain individuals are at a higher risk of contracting some diseases. Thus, it can be effectively applied to studying acute or chronic diseases, hence the interest in Cox regression by the medical science field. The Cox event history model mainly focuses on the hazard function, which produces the probability of an event occurring randomly at random times or at a specific period or instance in time.

The basic Cox event history model can be summarized by the following function:

$$h(t) = h_0(t)e^{(b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + K + b_nX_n)}$$

Where; $h(t)$ = rate of hazard

$h_0(t)$ = baseline hazard function

bX 's = coefficients and covariates.

Cox proportional hazard can be classified mainly under three models: nonparametric, semi-parametric and parametric. Non-parametric: The non-parametric model does not make any assumptions about the hazard function or the variables affecting it. Consequently, only a limited number of variable types can be handled with the help of a non-parametric model. This type of model involves the analysis of empirical data showing changes over a period of time and cannot handle continuous variables. Semi-parametric: Similar to the non-parametric model, the semi-parametric model also does not make any assumptions about the shape of the hazard function or the variables affecting it. What makes this model different is that it assumes the rate of the hazard is proportional over a period of time. The estimates for the hazard function shape can be derived empirically as well. Multivariate analyses are supported by semi-parametric models and are often considered a more reliable fitting method for use in a Cox event history analysis.

Parametric: In this model, the shape of the hazard function and the variables affecting it are determined in advance. Multivariate analyses of discrete and continuous explanatory variables are supported by the parametric model. However, if the hazard function shape is incorrectly estimated, then there is a chance that the results could be biased. Parametric models are frequently used to analyze the nature of time dependency. It is also particularly useful for predictive modeling, because the shape of the baseline hazard function can be determined correctly by the parametric model.

Pandemics are wide-ranging outbreaks of infectious disease that can rapidly increase morbidity and mortality over a wide geographic area and cause significant economic, social, and political disruption. Evidence suggests that the likelihood of pandemics has increased over the past century because of increased global travel and integration, urbanization, changes in land use, and greater exploitation of the natural environment (Jones et al., 2008). These trends likely will continue and will intensify. Significant policy attention has focused on the need to identify and limit emerging outbreaks that might lead to pandemics and to expand and sustain investment to build preparedness and health capacity (Hamburg et al., 2003).

According to Madhav et al. (2017), pandemic primarily is geographic, it joining together multiple, distinct types of events and public health threats, all of which have their own severity, frequency, and other disease characteristics. Each type of event requires its own optimal preparedness and response strategy; however this chapter also discusses common prerequisites for effective response. The variety of pandemic threats is driven by the great diversity of pathogens and their interaction with humans. Pathogens vary across multiple dimensions, including the mechanism and dynamics of disease transmission, severity, and differentiability of associated morbidities. These and other factors determine whether cases will be identified and contained rapidly or whether an outbreak will spread (Fraser et al., 2004). As a result, pathogens with pandemic potential also vary widely in the scale of their potential health, economic, and sociopolitical impacts as well as the resources, capacities, and strategies required for mitigation.

According to Bill Gate, (2020), nearly all respiratory viruses (a group that includes COVID) are seasonal. This would mean there are fewer infections in the summer, which might lull us into complacency when the fall comes. This is a matter of degree. Because we see coronavirus spreading in Australia and other places in the Southern hemisphere, where the seasons are the opposite of theirs, we already know the virus is not as seasonal as influenza is. Computer models show that if there are a lot of people who are asymptomatic but infectious, it is much harder to open up without resurgence in cases. There is a lot of disagreement about how much infection comes from these sources, but we do know that many people with the virus don't report symptoms, and some portion of those might end up transmitting it.

Understanding the dynamics here will help us weigh the risks of opening schools. It is a complicated subject because even if young people don't get sick as often, they might still spread the disease to others. Bill Gate (2020). Some countries are taking the temperature of lots of people as an initial screening tool. If doing this helps us find more potential cases, we could use it at airports and large gatherings. We need to target the tests we have at the people at greatest risk since we don't have enough tests for everyone.

Materials and Methods

This section deals with the method of data collection, variable under study, response variable and method of data analysis. The data were extracted from the Nigeria control for disease centre (<http://www.ncdc.ng.com>). The data consists of confirmed cases, discharged cases, death results in Isolation center, infected patients and followed up for the outcomes of either the event (death) or censored (withdrawal from treatment, stopped attending the clinic or loss of follow up till end of study time).

Variables of the Study

The following are the variable that the researcher will put into consideration, which are majorly 4 (four) in number and as follow confirmed cases, confirmed death, discharge cases and total active cases

The Response Variable

The response or outcome variable in this study is the survival time measured (in months) from the date of the isolation, treatment's starts until the date of the patient's death or discharged.

The Predictor Variable

The predictor or explanatory variables in survival data analysis are called covariates. These are

variables which are assumed to influence the survival of COVID 19 infected patients and are given below as following: Confirmed Cases, Discharged Cases, Death, Total Active.

The survival function is $S(t) = 1 - F(t)$, or the probability that a person or machine or a business lasts longer than t time units. Here $F(t)$ is the usual distribution function; in this context, it gives the probability that a thing lasts less than or equal to t time units. The hazard function is $\lambda(t) = f(t)/S(t)$.

The Kaplan-Meier survival probability is calculated using the formula:

$$S_{t+1} = \frac{S_t^x (N_t + 1 - D_t + 1)}{N_t + 1}$$

.where: S_t = Survival Probability

N_t = Number at risk

D_t = Number of death

The Cox regression model is based on the hazard function. Mathematically, the Cox model is written as follows (Van Dijk et al., 2008): $H(t) = H_0(t) \times \exp[b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_k X_k]$

where x_1, \dots, x_k represents the predictor variables and $H_0(t)$ is the baseline hazard at time t , which is the hazard of an individual having the predictors set to zero. By computing the exponential of the regression coefficient " b_1, \dots, b_k " (directly provided by the software), we can calculate the HR of a given risk factor or predictor in the model. For example, if the risk factor x_1 is dichotomous and it is codified "1" if present (exposed) and "0" if absent (unexposed), the expression $\exp^{(b_1)}$ (where $\exp = 2.7183$) can be interpreted as the estimated increase in the HR of the event in patients with the risk factor compared to those without the same risk factor; this is applied by assuming exposed and unexposed patients are similar for all the other covariates included in the model. If the risk factor is a continuous variable and it is directly related to the incidence rate of a given event (e.g., age in years as a risk factor for mortality), the HR will be interpreted as an increase in the hazard rate of death due to a 1-year increase in age. Thus, if a study reports a HR of 1.03 for age, it implies that the hazard rate of the event of interest increases by 3% for each year increase in age. If the risk factor is a continuous variable and it is inversely related to the incidence rate of a given event (e.g., albumin in g/dL, a protective biomarker of nutritional status, as a predictor of death), the HR associated with albumin is interpreted as the decrease of the hazard rate of the event due to a 1 g/dL increase in albumin. Thus, if a study reports a HR of albumin of 0.85, it implies that the hazard rate of the event decreases by 15% for each 1 g/dL increase in albumin.

Result

In this chapter, the results of the study are described and the analysis of the data presented.

Analysis was done using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 9.0. The results describe information on the subjects under study and how different predictors influence the outcome of interest by performing survival analysis using Kaplan – Meier and Cos regression method.

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Table 1: Kaplan- Meier survival analysis

Regression	Statistics				
	Estimate	Censored	Lower bound	Upper bound	No of Event
Confirmed death case on confirmed cases	51%	98% of 23227	51	51	457
Confirmed death on Discharge cases	48%	89% of 21183	48	48	2501
Confirmed death on Total Active	49%	93% of 22045	49	49	1639

Confirmed death on Total Active with likelihood of 17053.298,50086.745 and 32908.956 respectively.

The table above shows that a total number of event 457 and 98% out of 23227 were censored and 51% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 51:51 respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, while a total number of event 2501 and 89% of 21183 were censored and 48% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 48:48 respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases also a total number of event 1639 and 93% of 22045 were censored and 49% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 49:98 respectively for Confirmed death on total active. While Confirmed death cases on confirmed cases have the highest censored of 98% followed by Confirmed death on total active with 93%

Table 2: Cos Regression

Regression	Confirmed death case on confirmed cases	Confirmed death on Discharge cases	Confirmed death on Total Active
Unweighted Censored	60% of 66	49% of 54	53% of 59
Weighted Censored	96% of 22836	89% of 21183	93% of 22045
Event Unweighted	28% of 31	39% of 43	34% of 38
Event weighted	4% of 848	89% of 21183	7% of 1639
Likelihood	17053.298	50086.745	32908.956
Missing Values	13% of 14	13% of 14	13% of 14

The table above shows that a total number of event both weighted and unweighted are 4%(848) and 28%(31) respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, total number of event both weighted and unweighted are 11%(2504) and 39%(43) respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases and total number of event both weighted and unweighted are 7%(1639) and 38%(38) respectively for Confirmed death on Total Active while weighted and unweighted censored are 96%(22836) and 60%(66) respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, weighted and unweighted censored are 89%(21183) and 49%(54) respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases and weighted and unweighted censored are 89%(21183) and 49%(54) respectively for weighted and unweighted censored are 93%(22045) and 53%(59) respectively for Confirmed death on Total Active and Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, Confirmed death on Discharge cases for

Discussion

In this work, we examined the survival analysis of COVID-19 patients who were isolated in Rivers State and were followed up for 6 (six) months. The variables used in this work include confirmed cases, confirmed death, discharge cases and total active on COVID-19 infected patients who are on treatment statistical package for the social science was used for examining the survival analysis. Non-parametric and parametric survival models were used for the analysis. The pattern (distribution) of survival times of the cohort under study was done using the Kaplan-Meier (K-M) estimator and Log rank test was used to compare patterns of time to event across groups.

Conclusion

From the result in this work, 23684 patients were collected (experienced the event) while number of event both weighted and unweighted are 4%(848) and 28%(31) respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, total number of event both weighted and unweighted are 11%(2504) and 39%(43) respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases and total number of event both weighted and unweighted are 7%(1639) and 38%(38) respectively for Confirmed death on Total Active while weighted and unweighted censored are 96%(22836) and 60% (66) respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, weighted and unweighted censored are 89%(21183) and 49% (54) respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases and weighted and unweighted censored are 89%(21183) and 49% (54) respectively for weighted and unweighted censored are 93%(22045) and 53% (59) respectively for Confirmed death on Total Active and Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, Confirmed death on Discharge cases for Confirmed death on Total Active with likelihood of 17053.298,50086.745 and 32908.956 respectively Cox regression. While total number of event 457 and 98% out 23227 were censored and 51% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 51:51 respectively for Confirmed death case on confirmed cases, while a total number of event 2501 and 89% of 21183 were censored and 48% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 48:48 respectively for Confirmed death on Discharge cases also a total number of event 1639 and 93% of 22045 were censored and 49% estimated and lower and upper boundary of 49:98 respectively for Confirmed death on total active. While Confirmed death cases on confirmed cases have the highest censored of 98% followed by Confirmed death on total active with 93% using the K-M plots.

Recommendation

This work recommends that consideration should be given more on confirmed cases for COVID-19 survival and also further studies should be carried out in the case of left censored observations using these models.

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Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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